

UNREASONABLE DEGRADATION OF THE MARINE ENVIRONMENT - WHAT IS IT?

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ABSTRACT

A strategy is presented for quantifying the extent of pollutant degradation in coastal environments and ecosystems. Twelve indices are recommended as efficient and geographically comparable ways to characterize pollutant degradation, given adequate interpretation of the index values. The indices are also recommended as scales of degradation along which "serious" or "unreasonable" degradation, in a social or legal sense, can be defined by legislative, regulatory and judicial processes.

1. INTRODUCTION

That once-natural coastal environments have been degraded measurably is an objective, verifiable statement. Whether or not they are degraded "unreasonably" in a legal or broad societal sense hinges upon both the objective nature of the degradation and subjective perceptions of its acceptability. Federal law, regulations of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the Army Corps of Engineers (COE), and the judicial process are now attempting to guide the equitable resolution of this issue.

However, without legally-formalized, quantitative definitions of how much pollution or how much impact is acceptable there is no obvious basis for constraints on pollution. Lacking such definitions government must continue to make *ad hoc* decisions about waste disposal in coastal waters. For instance, dredged materials, no matter what their total toxicant loadings, may be dumped at sea if they pass a series of toxicity and bioaccumulation tests. But there is no evident relationship between the tests and protection against any particular degree of ecosystem impact. Similarly, the variety of guidelines which must be met for the discharge of pollutants to coastal waters under the Clean Water Act of 1977 are not linked to objective measures of "unreasonable degradation" or "irreparable harm" (Federal Register, 45(194):65942-65954). Some of

these decision criteria have been successfully challenged because they are not demonstrably related to unreasonable environmental or ecosystem damage. One such challenge with respect to sewage sludge dumping has been recently upheld in Federal court.

In 1977, the Marine Protection, Research, and Sanctuaries Act (P.L. 92-532, commonly referred to as the Ocean Dumping Act) was amended so that ocean dumping of sewage sludge "which may unreasonably degrade or endanger human health, welfare, amenities or the marine environment, ecological systems or economic potentialities" (33 U.S.C. 1412a) would not be allowed after December 31, 1981. The EPA interpreted this requirement to prohibit all ocean dumping of sewage sludge. This interpretation was challenged by the City of New York in New York City v. EPA, 17ERC1181 (S.D.N.Y. 1981).

New York City contended that the mandated 1981 deadline should not apply to its sewage sludge because the sewage sludge being dumped did not "unreasonably degrade" the marine environment of the New York Bight. The City argued that in determining whether ocean dumping was unreasonable, EPA must evaluate the effects of dumping at the dumpsite, and of effects from alternative disposal methods. The City also held that the available land-based alternatives are less socially and economically desirable than ocean dumping. The City contended that Congress defined sewage sludge with the intent that the definition should be used in the development of criteria for ocean dumping of sewage sludge, and that EPA had failed to do this. The U.S. District Court (Southern District of New York) ruled in New York City's favor. The decision on the case was that the 1981 deadline on ocean dumping of sewage sludge would remain intact. However, the decision allows the continued ocean dumping of sewage sludge until there is an evaluation of whether the practice causes "unreasonable degradation" in the context of all relevant environmental, social, and economic factors enumerated in Section 102 of the Act.

This is but one example. The ocean dumping criteria for dredged materials dumped in the New York Bight have been relaxed without a court test because the criteria are not related quantitatively to environmental impact. Probably most waste discharge and dumping criteria for coastal waters could be challenged along similar lines, partially because we have no quantitative, socially-agreed definition of how much pollution or how much impact is too much.

A major stimulus for redefining "unreasonable degradation" of marine environments stems from a request by the Congress to help in revising the Ocean Dumping Act. A quantitative definition of "unreasonable degradation," if widely agreed upon, would also be valuable guidance for related legislation -- new and revised. Such a definition would also be valuable to the courts and regulatory agencies.

It is also useful to consider how much marine pollution is enough in order to set rational limits which are understood by the general public. We are often asked by the layman, "how serious is the pollution out there?" Only if the layman can be given straightforward answers can he be expected to participate effectively in establishing socially-acceptable limits on pollution.

Definition of "unreasonable degradation" will require scientific, social, and legal efforts. A contribution to this definition -- a scale for measuring degrees of coastal degradation -- is presented here as part of the scientific input. Our contribution describes and justifies 12 indices of degradation of the marine environment and ecological systems (as defined in the Ocean Dumping Act) that may be useful in formulating a quantifiable definition of "unreasonable degradation."

The scope of this preliminary paper is restricted specifically to contaminant effects in coastal and open-ocean waters. Estuaries and the Great Lakes are not considered, but the approaches outlined could be adapted to these environments. This scope is broader than effects of the ocean dumping of contaminants (the scope of the Ocean Dumping Act). Simultaneous consideration of all waste inputs is necessary. This is important because the "unreasonableness" of a particular dumping activity, for instance, cannot be assessed without understanding oceanic impacts from other, adjacent waste inputs.

2. STRATEGY

There have been several efforts to define the pollution status and trends in aquatic water quality. Most such efforts have dealt with

freshwaters, but they are relevant to our task [1, 2].

Three distinct kinds of degradation are of interest: public health impacts, ecosystem degradation, and degradation of coastal environments. In selecting features of coastal environments and ecosystems to characterize degradation, we have excluded those which might be viewed as of marginal significance in a social or legal context. Attributes selected seem to be potentially significant enough to cause 'unreasonable degradation or danger to human health, welfare, amenities, or the marine environment, ecological systems, or economic potentialities' (1977 amendments to the Ocean Dumping Act) or to constitute "(1) significant adverse changes in ecosystem diversity productivity and stability of the biological community within the area of discharge and surrounding biological communities, (2) threat to human health through consumption of exposed aquatic organisms, or (3) loss of aesthetic, recreational, scientific or economic values which is unreasonable in relation to the benefit derived from the discharge" (1972 amendments to the Federal Water Pollution Control Act).

Some of the recommended indices are already used routinely in many areas (e.g., fecal coliform concentrations in water). Most others are based upon measurements of proven reliability in research findings (e.g., fecundity of fish and shellfish).

Criteria for index selection

Three principal criteria were applied in deciding upon the most useful indices of ecosystem degradation resulting from pollution. First, the set of indices must be capable of detecting any plausible form of serious environmental or ecosystem degradation. Any particular index cannot be relied upon to reflect all or a large portion of significant ecosystem stresses. Indeed, any one index provides information about only a small fraction of potential ecosystem stresses. Therefore, several indices are required to offer reasonable assurance that significant degradation is detected promptly.

The indices must also be sensitive to pollutant stresses, and relatively insensitive to other factors. Almost all measurable properties of ecosystems are responsive to a wide variety of ecosystem stresses other than pollution (e.g., fishing, human physical disturbances, and natural variability of several kinds). It is seldom possible to ascribe to these changes in properties the fractional contributions of natural factors, pollution, and other

factors. Hence it is essential to select indices which are known to respond rather significantly to pollutant stresses, and which are not expected to change significantly without pollutant stresses.

The third criterion for useful indices is that they be realistically available. Many otherwise valuable indices rely upon measurements which are probably not affordable. Other potentially valuable indices require measurements for which reliable techniques do not exist. So, indices are favored when they require inexpensive measurements, particularly if such measurements are already being made commonly or routinely.

Form of the indices

The indices described below are structured to provide comparable, numerical scales of intensity for specific manifestations of degradation. Each index ranges from zero (indicating normal conditions) to large, but finite, values (indicating pronounced degradation). In addition, specified "inhibiting" or "unsafe" index values are based upon scientifically verifiable implications for public health or for continuity of the ecosystem. For the two indices relating to public health, the "unsafe" bounds (or toxicant concentrations of concern in marine food organisms) are those defined by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration or some other governmental health regulatory body. For all but two of the indices of ecological degradation, the "inhibiting" (or "enriching" in two instances) bounds are those known or expected to impair reproduction. The "unsafe" bounds for the two remaining indices are extremes of benthic invertebrate community changes and exceptionally high prevalence of disease in fish or shellfish, both of which are generally considered "unsafe" for the affected species by scientific authorities. Other, equally objective, criteria could be used to define thresholds of different "inhibiting" or "unsafe" conditions. We have chosen to use rather serious effects, recognizing that several biotic impacts will generally be evident at lower toxicant concentrations than those causing the impacts described above.

Four of the indices indicate the extent to which contaminants approach concentrations which inhibit the reproductive success of marine biota. Wherever reliable estimates of background contaminant concentrations (pre-industrial concentrations, say prior to 1800) can be made, they are subtracted from the "observed" and "inhibiting" or "unsafe" concentrations in order to clearly index the existing post-industrial concentrations as a

fraction of post-industrial concentrations which would be inhibiting or unsafe. This provides a much clearer indication than indices of total contaminant levels of how much additional environmental contamination would be required to reach "inhibiting" or "unsafe" concentrations. The general form of these indices is:

$$I = \frac{\text{observed concentration} - \text{background concentration}}{\text{inhibiting concentration} - \text{background concentration}}$$

The general form of the indices of reproductive effects is simply:

$$I = 0.05/P$$

where: P = the probability that estimated differences in fecundity or mortality are due to factors other than pollutants, and

0.05 is a constant which causes the indices to assume values of one or more if statistically significant ($P < 0.05$)

Individual indices must be based upon measurements which can be combined yet remain interpretable. For instance, all but two of the indices we propose involve measurement of several contaminants, or several species, or several contaminants in several species. The combined effects of several toxicants, in terms of both public health and ecological effects, are so poorly understood that no useful rationale is evident for any particular index of combined toxicant effects. Consequently these indices use as their basis the single toxicant which appears to be most damaging (or closest to damaging). Yet, if cadmium concentrations, say, in the sediments of a region appear to be more ecologically damaging than any other toxicant (and constitute the basis for the index of contaminant burdens in sediments), it is still important to estimate how close other concentrated contaminants are to being ecologically damaging. The suggested strategy to summarize these estimates efficiently is to estimate "index" values for each contaminant of concern, and display them as a histogram along an axis of index severity. The areal extent of each index value should also be indicated.

Time and space scales

Values of the indices, per se, indicate only the degree or intensity of pollutant impact. The significance of impact also depends greatly upon its size, location, and duration. If waste were discharged into a one-acre fishing pond sterilizing one half of it, there would be much more ecosystem degradation than if the same discharge occurred in the middle of the Pacific Ocean. If the effect of a waste discharge is evident for only thirty minutes it degrades considerably less than an effect that persists for a year. Obviously, considerations of space and time scales are inherent in assessing the ecosystem impact of waste disposal schemes. Also obviously, these considerations are never so simple as comparing fishing ponds with the Pacific Ocean, and half hours to years.

Charts appear to be the most informative and efficient format to display the location and areal extent of degradation. For each index the high, intermediate, and low values may generally be contoured. This illustration of gradients from the highest (most severe) to the lowest index values will generally be more informative than an average regional value which fails to define both highly degraded and undegraded areas.

3. THE INDICES

The indices which seem to have the most utility for broadly indicating degradation of coastal and oceanic environments and ecosystems are:

1. Toxicant concentrations in marine foods relative to public health criteria
2. Toxicant concentrations in biota relative to population size impacts
3. Contaminant burdens in sediments
4. Toxicant concentrations in the water column
5. Fecal coliform concentrations in water
6. Benthic species composition and abundance
7. Fish/shellfish disease
8. Fecundity of fish/shellfish
9. Fatal genetic defects in eggs of fish/shellfish
10. Mortality in artificially spawned eggs of fish/shellfish

11. Marine birds and turtles - eggs per nest
12. Marine birds and turtles - eggs mortality

Depending upon the areal extent and duration of impact, degradation indices of less than one may well deserve consideration by regulatory agencies, legislatures, and the public. For instance, indices which indicate that toxicant concentrations in marine foods are close to public health hazards or are approaching the concentrations expected to impair reproductive success in harvested fishes might be considered "unreasonable."

Rationale for the indices

Index 1 indicates the extent to which specific toxicants of concern have become concentrated in marine foods through human activity. The index indicates how closely the toxicant concentrations approach the maximum standards established by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration or some other governmental health regulatory body. Estimated tissue concentrations are either available or readily measured regionally for the relatively few contaminants with defined limits. All of these contaminants are present in the edible tissues of fish and shellfish from coastal waters, sometimes in concentrations approaching those of concern. It does not seem safe to rule out any of the contaminants with defined criteria as being inconsequential in marine foods, at least in the near future. Thus, all contaminants for which maximum acceptable concentrations in marine foods have been formally defined, and which seem appropriate for the U.S., are considered in Index 1 (i.e., U.S. FDA - Aldrin/Dieldrin 0.3 ppm, mercury 1 ppm, PCBs 5 ppm, toxaphene 0.3 ppm, DDT 5 ppm, chlordane 0.3 ppm, heptachlor/heptachlor epoxide 0.3 ppm, and kepone 0.3 ppm; National Health and Medical Research Council of Australia - lead 2 ppm; and FAO/WHO of the United Nations - cadmium 0.04 to 0.05 ppm (all in wet weight)). The form of the index is given above.

The public health implications of combined effects from several toxicants are so poorly understood that no useful rationale is evident for any particular index of combined toxicant effects. Consequently, the value used for Index 1 is the largest index for any toxicant, averaged over the species measured but also noting any within-species ratios which approach or exceed one.

The second index indicates the degree to which toxicants are approaching or exceeding concentrations that inhibit the reproductive success of marine biota. The index does not

embrace the wide variety of sublethal contaminant effects exhibited by coastal biota unless they are quantitatively linked to reproductive success. Thus the index does not consider diseases or the host of physiological responses to contaminants, many of which probably tend to reduce population size, if quantitative evidence for population effects is lacking.

The form of the second index is similar to the index of toxicant concentrations in marine food organisms relative to public health. The unacceptable concentrations used in the first index are replaced by the concentration(s) in flesh or organs that have been shown to inhibit or may be expected to inhibit reproduction.

As was true with man for Index 1, knowledge of combined toxicant effects on marine organisms is not adequate to define an integrated index of toxicant effects. Evidence indicates that additive, synergistic, and antagonistic effects all commonly result from pairs of toxicants. Further, almost no observations exist on the combined effects of several toxicants, the typical real-life situation. Consequently, the highest index value for a particular toxicant within a species becomes Index 2, also summarizing as histograms the index values for other species and toxicants analyzed.

The array of toxicants used in this index is regionally defined. All toxicants are considered that are sufficiently concentrated in water or sediments of the region to represent possible limitations upon the size of any marine population.

In contrast to Index 1, the species selected for Index 2 are not intended to be representative of all marine organisms or of just marine food organisms. Existing knowledge provides some indication of the species at greatest risk from toxicants. Principal management interest is in species which are being limited in number by toxicants -- and in their commercial, recreational and ecological significance, not in an average property of coastal biota. Hence, it seems important that Index 2 be used to assess as many coastal species as possible in which population sizes may be closest to limitations by toxicants. Marine and shore zone birds commonly appear to be among the taxa most susceptible to population declines from toxicants. Birds and other taxa judged to be the most probable candidates for toxicant-induced population impacts should be assessed regionally.

Index 3 is designed to indicate the degree of contaminant concentration in sediments.

While such concentrations do not yet allow reliable prediction of particular ecosystem effects, the index has two valuable features which commend its use. The index is an unusually reliable indicator of spatial scales of contamination and, hence, the areal extent of probable impacts upon benthic fishes and invertebrates. Consequently, spatial gradients defined by this index should be a most important criterion for preliminary definition and adequate sampling the "regions of interest" for bottom-living or bottom-feeding organisms used in some other indices. The second valuable feature of Index 3 is the likelihood that some features of ecosystem degradation will be broadly predictable from high values of the index alone. Within a few years it seems likely that we will understand much more reliably the kinds and degrees of sediment contamination which lead to broadly predictable degradation of benthic communities, disease in bottom-living organisms, toxicant uptake by bottom-feeding fish and shellfish, and avoidance or attraction by particular bottom fishes. Availability of the data necessary for computing this index, gathered over large areas, could hasten our ability to make such broad but useful predictions.

The index provides separate estimates of enrichment effects (as measured by total organic carbon content) and toxic effects (including all toxicants having even potential ecosystem impact). Enrichment and toxic effects are calculated and portrayed separately, since their combination is difficult to interpret.

The index uses measurements of each toxicant concentration that might possibly inhibit the normal reproduction of the most sensitive species of the region minus background. Thus each toxicant is weighted in terms of the extent to which its post-industrial accumulation approaches concentrations leading to reproductive inhibition.

Index 4, a measure of ecological risk from contaminants in the water column, is another valuable measure of spatial contamination. The index is comparable to that of sediment contamination, with two differences. Since pre-industrial toxicant concentrations are not reliably estimated in water, no adjustments are made to concentrations measured in water. Also, the availability and effects of most toxicants likely to affect pelagic organisms have been assessed authoritatively in the EPA report series, "Ambient Water Quality Criteria." So long as the 24-hour average "criterion" values of these assessments remain authoritative, they constitute the highest "safe" concentrations which ensure against damage to marine

organisms. Thus, each toxicant is indexed by dividing its measured concentration by its EPA "criterion" or "safe" concentration. The largest ratio is selected as the index of toxicant concentrations in the water column, and the ratios for the remaining toxicants are displayed as a histogram.

The fifth index is a measure of human pathogen contamination of coastal waters. The widely-used concentration of fecal coliform bacteria is simply expressed as a ratio of the typical standard for bathing waters (200 MPN/100 ml).

Despite the several drawbacks of fecal coliform bacteria as indicators of human pathogens in seawater, they remain useful indicators. More reliable indicator measurements are not anticipated for most coastal waters in the near future.

Index 6 is designed to measure departures from normal benthic species composition and abundance. "Normal" benthic community structure is taken as the best available characterization of the pre-industrial communities expected at the depths and for the sediment grain sizes in the region of interest. Such characterization is sometimes possible by taking "control" samples from nearly uncontaminated, but otherwise comparable, sediments. However, all nearshore fine sediments are contaminated in some regions, necessitating a more plausible reconstruction of pre-industrial normal benthic community structure from the earliest reliable benthic reports.

This index is defined as the mean of four somewhat independent measures of pollutant-induced degradation commonly observed in benthic macrofaunal communities:

1. changes in species composition as measured by the Jaccard coefficient of similarity,
2. reductions in the numbers of species normally present,
3. reductions in the numbers of amphipods normally present, and
4. increases in abundance of the most numerically dominant species.

Degradation of benthic macrofaunal communities can be measured rather reliably and provides a useful indication of degraded food sources for demersal fishes.

Higher than normal prevalence of disease in marine organisms has been associated with pollution. Index 7 is an integrated measure of the extent to which fish and shellfish diseases in a region approach their highest known prevalencies in coastal waters.

The form of the index is the ratio of observed minus background disease prevalence to maximum observed minus background prevalence. The average of ratios for all diseases accurately estimated is taken as the index value.

Estimates of prevalence are available for several diseases: black gill and shell erosion, epidermal neoplasia, internal lesions in finfishes, lymphocystis, ulcers, fin erosion, pigmentation anomalies, and skeletal malformations. The prevalence of these diseases over large areas can be determined rather inexpensively because large numbers of fish and shellfish can be examined quickly for the presence of these diseases.

The remaining five indices are designed to detect contaminant-associated impairment of reproduction and early-life survival in harvestable marine plants, shellfish, finfish, birds, and turtles. Emphasis is placed upon the reproductive process and early-life stages because they are generally impaired by toxicants at lower concentrations than are adults [3, 4, 5, 6]. These indices make use of reliably detected pollutant-impaired reproductive success or early larval mortality because of their unequivocal significance in reducing population sizes. A variety of sublethal pollutant effects may lead to reduced population sizes as well and at lower toxicant concentrations, but the evidence is seldom clear and is seldom accorded much weight in costly environmental decisions.

The relationship between impaired reproduction and population declines is seldom known quantitatively. Hence, in contrast with the previously described indices, these indices of pollutant-induced impairment of reproduction lack a direct measure of the ecosystem response of principal concern (i.e., pollutant-induced constraints on population size). However, any pollutant-induced reductions in normal fecundity or early-life survival would tend to reduce population size. Consequently, statistically significant ($P < .05$) reductions in normal fecundity and reproductive success are used as the "unsafe" criteria for indices 8 through 12. Only such reductions that are reliably attributed to pollutants are useful for the indices. The experimental designs for indices 8-12 must be adequate to detect most pollutant effects which are present. The probability of not detecting effects which are present, Type II error, should be kept to 0.3 or less by adequate sampling and other features of experimental design.

Index 8 is based upon the observed numbers of mature eggs (or follicles in the case of

seaweeds) relative to normal fecundity adjusted for weights of the parents.

Because the numbers of eggs per female are reliably correlated with female body weight, the analysis of covariance is recommended as the most powerful test for differences between fecundity of normal and contaminated fish/shellfish. (The number of eggs per female is regressed upon female body weight, for a normal, uncontaminated sample versus an observed, contaminated sample.) The covariance comparison of greatest interest is that between the elevations of the normal and observed regression lines, i.e., is the normal population more fecund?

Index 8 is defined in terms of the probability that sample, measured reductions in fecundity of contaminated organisms are not real population differences, but are due to sampling variability. As this probability becomes smaller Index 8 becomes larger, and the index becomes one as the probability (P) reaches 0.05 ($\text{Index } 8 = 0.05/P$). If the slopes or residual variances of the two regression lines differ it will be necessary to analyze the residual variances relative to contaminant burdens in the females. This is a useful analysis in any case, to rigorously assess the relationship between pollutant burdens and fecundity of individual females.

At least six fish and shellfish species should be examined within each region of interest. The individuals selected should have distributions which are well defined relative to environmental pollutant concentrations. The largest, reliable reduction in fecundity is taken as the index value.

The incidence of fatal genetic defects in the eggs of fish and shellfish (Index 9) appears to be a useful measure of pollutant degradation [7]. The index has the advantage of being based upon field measurements that can estimate both pollutant-induced and natural mortality. The incidence of fatal genetic defects is estimated within the region of interest and in a relatively uncontaminated, background region. Tests of significant differences are then conducted between the sample incidence in the background region and one or more homogeneous areas within the contaminated region of interest. The form of Index 9 is $0.05/P$, where P is the probability that estimated differences in mortality incidence are due to chance.

The measurement strategy and form of indices 10 through 12 are identical with indices 8 and 9. The mortalities of early life stages of fish, shellfish, turtles and birds are estimated in contaminated and relatively

uncontaminated regions. The corresponding indices are functions of the estimated probabilities of contaminant effects.

The measures of mortality for indices 9 through 12 have been applied successfully in particular situations. All the measurements needed are rather inexpensive, or entail analysis of data gathered for other purposes.

4. APPLICATION OF THE INDICES

The indices, per se, represent the intensity of environmental and ecosystem degradation in 12 different respects. All indices are mapped onto charts because both the locations and sizes of degraded areas are consistently needed for interpretation. In many situations additional scientific information will be necessary to fully interpret index values and the areal extents which they characterize.

In practice these indices are useful on different spatial scales. Indices 2 through 6 commonly have rather localized gradients, hence will be particularly useful for site specific (e.g., ocean dumping and waste outfall) and broader scale issues. Indices 7-9, as applied to shellfish, are also appropriate for site-specific degradation. In contrast, indices 1, 7-9 (for motile forms), and 10-12 generally have regional or even global gradients. The latter will generally indicate the degradation of an entire region from several waste sources, but will seldom indicate much about local waste sources. However, the indices which can show localized impacts are just as capable of characterizing degradation regionally or globally.

There is no apparent, useful strategy for combining the 12 indices into a single index of degradation. Any type of function that combines two or more indices results in the loss of information about particular contaminant effects, and the resulting single index will rarely be interpretable.

Monitoring offers the best strategy for gaining the recommended core of measurements needed to characterize the degree of degradation in U.S. coastal waters. Sufficiently precise estimates of pollutant impacts which employ comparable measurements over our coasts require some degree of national monitoring coordination [8]. These recommended indices, or modifications agreed upon through peer review, define the core monitoring measurements that seem to be most useful in characterizing coastal degradation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Simple indices of coastal degradation seem to offer promise as quantitative tools for guiding legislatures, regulatory agencies, and the courts, and for informing the public. The need for full interpretation of indices remains, as would be true of any form of pollutant impact information.

There are four apparent advantages to the use of indices: 1) They are perhaps the simplest way to summarize pollutant effects. 2) Given the use of inexpensive and already tested measurements, indices are the cheapest way to characterize degradation. 3) Use of a common set of indices would ensure that nationally comparable measures of degradation were available. 4) If, as we propose, the scale of each index includes an "unsafe range" or "range of concern," defined on objective bases, the index values would seem to be more informative for policy makers and courts than measures of degradation which lack such ranges.

The principal disadvantage of indices seems to be hypothetical. That is, indices can be presented superficially and used uncritically in decisionmaking. This potential problem seems no more difficult to avoid than any other mode of superficial or unbalanced ecological assessment. It is true that the original measurements are lost in the process of deriving the indices (with the exception of Index 5), but if the original measurements are germane they must be included as part of any adequate assessment strategy.

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7. REFERENCES

1. Thomas W. A., G. Goldstein, and W. H. Wilcox, Biological Indicators of Environmental Quality. Ann Arbor Science, Ann Arbor, Mich., 254 p., 1973.
2. Pikul, R., Development of environmental indices. pp. 103-121. In: J. W. Pratt [Ed.] Statistical and Mathematical Aspects of Pollution Problems. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1974.
3. Vernberg, W. B., A. Calabrese, F. P. Thurberg, and F. J. Vernberg, Marine Pollution: Functional Responses. Academic Press, New York, 454 p., 1979.
4. Lockwood, A. P. M., Effects of Pollutants on Marine Organisms. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 193 p., 1976.
5. Hart, C. W. Jr., S. L. H. Fuller, Pollution Ecology of Estuarine Invertebrates. Academic Press, New York, 406 p., 1979.
6. Howe, M. A., R. B. Clapp, and J. S. Weske, Marine and Coastal Birds. MESA New York Bight Atlas Monograph 31. New York Sea Grant Institute, Albany, N. Y., 87 p., 1978.
7. Longwell, A. C. and J. B. Hughes, Cytologic, cytogenetic, and developmental state of Atlantic mackerel eggs from sea surface waters of the New York Bight, and prospects for biological effects monitoring with ichthyoplankton. Rapp. P.v. Reun. Cons. int. Explor. Mer, Vol. 179, pp. 275-291, 1980.
8. Segar, D. A., An Assessment of Great Lakes and Ocean Pollution Monitoring in the United States. NOAA, Office of Marine Pollution Assessment. Working Paper No. 7: Federal Plan for Ocean Pollution Research Development and Monitoring, FY1981-1985. Boulder, Colo., 53 p., 1981.